

M.Sc in Social Data Science
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Summary

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Gender interruption spotting: A proof-of-concept using audio machine learning to detect gender dynamics of simultaneous speech events in recorded conversation

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ABSTRACT

There is a long history of research interest in gender and conversation interruptions, especially about what it means for equality and power. Despite the extensive literature, there is wide disagreement on gender patterns due to methodological differences and the constraints of qualitative research designs. Only a recent few studies have begun to use computational methods, which have the potential to improve validity and generalizability to studies about interruptions. This paper is a proof-of-concept that documents the first attempt to investigate how audio machine learning using a neural network with a transformer architecture on large audio datasets can add to research on gender-based interruption patterns, especially compared to existing text-based methods. Audio classifiers trained on a novel dataset of 3,076 examples of interruptions and non-interruptions show promising results, with classification metrics from 0.66 to 0.87. This suggests that it is possible to detect interruptions including the gender dynamic of the speakers based on the audio signature of the audio events. A rule-based text classifier tested on automatically generated transcripts performed much worse, underscoring the unique potential of audio methods. Future developments on this method (larger training dataset, modified operationalization, and larger models) could create a reliable classifier for detecting interruptions with their gender dynamic, enabling a greatly expanded range of research opportunities into this phenomenon.

1. Introduction

Conversation interruptions and their relationship to social power dynamics has been a subject of social science and linguistic research for decades. Important contributions to this research emphasize the relationship between institutionalized power structures and interruption dynamics relating to social divisions such as race and gender.

Despite the number of studies on interruptions, most face significant limitations in generalizability as the majority of papers rely on qualitative analysis of small samples. The scientific community has also yet to agree on what kind of gender patterns, if any, exist in interruption behavior. This disagreement shows an opportunity for computational methods that enable the analysis of large datasets. Computational methods that take advantage of neural networks trained on large amounts of data could better account for the nuances that can affect findings on interruption behavior.

In this research I take a step towards testing whether this is possible. This paper documents the first exploration of the use of audio machine learning methods using neural networks with transformer technology to identify interruptions by gender. I fine-tuned audio neural network classifiers with a novel manually annotated audio dataset of 3,076 interruption

examples and counterexamples to identify these events directly in the recorded audio. Results show good model performance on out-of-sample data during leave-one-out cross validation in the ability to identify an interruption, indicating that the model would be reliable in detecting interruptions in unseen podcasts. Performance of a second audio classifier trained to detect the gender dynamic in an interruption is less strong, but still indicates that the task is possible. The gender classifier greatly outperformed text-based methods (including the same used in a recent social science paper to detect social interruption patterns). These rule-based text methods were applied to transcripts of a subset of my audio training dataset in order to understand the comparative utility of audio-based methods.

As a proof-of-concept, I apply the audio classifier to infer interruptions by gender in 43 unseen podcast episodes, showing how this tool can be applied in the future to well-sampled data to produce valid social-science findings on gender differences in interruption. This provides a first step towards enabling future research into varying interruption dynamics. Future applications could include classifying the interruptions by functional type (competitive, supportive, or neutral) and inferring accurate gender, age, or other differences in interruption behaviors and how that intersects with

variables such as topic of conversation or relationship between the speakers. This paper makes a significant contribution to the existing literature on interruption behavior by showing the potential of applying transformer-based audio classifiers.

2. Literature review

2.1. Conversational interruptions and power

In research and in common discourse, interruptions are highly associated as a competitive, aggressive way to control a conversation and exercise social power. James and Clarke point out that “the word ‘interruption,’ in ordinary usage and to most researchers, has negative connotations, implying violation of another's right to speak” (1993, p. 237). Mishler and Waxler call interruptions “a person-control strategy” that communicates messages such as “stop talking” or “I am no longer listening to what you say” (1968, 140). Octigan and Niederman, in their work *Male Dominance in Conversations*, consider interruptions “as a violation and a sign of conversational dominance” (1979 p. 52). West and Zimmerman claim that “conversations have implicit turn-taking rules” and interruptions are “violations” of these rules, but interruptions are about more than just the “organization of the conversation”; they are about power (1983, p. 4). “Having the floor in a conversation is a position of power,” as this person “sets the topic of conversation... has the predominant voice in setting the definition of the situation... [and] direct[s] the conversation (who will say what and when)” (West and Zimmerman 1983, p. 4). Therefore, interruptions are “a way of ‘doing’ power in face-to-face interaction” (West and Zimmerman 1983, p. 4).

2.2. Interruptions, power, and gender

West and Zimmerman (1983) connect interruptions as a practice of power to gender: “to the extent that power is implicated in what it means to be a man vis-a-vis a woman, it is a way of ‘doing’ gender as well” (1983, p. 4). In one of the most cited works showing that men interrupt more than women, Zimmerman and West (1975) emphasize the relationship between institutionalized power structures and interruptions in conversation, pointing out the relevance of interruption dynamics for social divisions such as race, age, and gender. Disproportionate use of interruptions as a way of exercising social power by social groups has been seen to have implications for both the psychosocial wellbeing of individuals and the functioning of society. Octigan and Niederman (1979) state,

This sort of conversational dominance, which is so subtle, subliminal, and well-woven into the fabric of

everyday interaction, can leave a woman feeling as though neither logic, nor wit, nor hard information can have any effect on the man to whom she is speaking; she can end up feeling shouted down and not understanding why (p. 51).

In a 1989 paper, Smith-Lovin and Brody emphasize how conversations reflect and maintain social inequalities, as they “import hierarchical structures from larger society and help perpetuate them by creating inequalities in the ability to accomplish interactional goals” (p. 424). They found that in task-oriented conversations, gender inequality was brought about by (a) attempts to use power and (b) differential success of these attempts.

Interruptions are still an important area of interest in the social sciences, as researchers continue to analyze interruption behavior and its relationship to social power dynamics including gender (see Ghilzai 2018; Pakzadian and Ashoori Tootkaboni 2018; Miller, and Sutherland 2023), as well as race and ethnic group minority/majority status (Leman and Ikoko 2010; Boyd, Collins and Ringhand 2024). Authors express the importance of understanding how issues of inequality and access to power are reflected through and reinforced by conversation dominance behavior. Jacobi and Schweers (2017), who found that women justices were disproportionately interrupted by their male colleagues during US supreme court oral arguments, pointed out the importance of understanding how these justices use interruptions to seek influence and affect the outcome of cases. Boyd, Collins, and Ringhand (2024) explain that “in political settings, interruptions enable control over the discussion and achievement of outcome goals” (p. 2). Differential access to influence in conversation based on social divisions such as gender or race could inhibit the efficacy of members of groups who are frequently interrupted, preventing them from successfully representing the needs and interests of social groups to which they belong in policymaking, resulting in policies that reinforce institutionalized inequalities.

2.3. Research gap

Despite the large body of research, there is disagreement and uncertainty about gender differences in initiating interruptions or being interrupted. Two prominent reviews of interruption literature illuminate what nuances are still left unaddressed: Anderson and Leaper’s 1998 *Meta-analyses of gender effects on conversational interruption* and James and Clarke in *Women, Men, and Interruptions: A Critical Review* in the 1993 book *Gender and conversational interaction* (edited by Deborah Tannen, ed.), one of the most comprehensive and respected works on gender in

conversation interaction. While even recent studies claim that a “long-standing body of work has shown that men employ a number of tactics in conversation—including interruption—to exert social dominance” citing the famous 1975 work by Zimmerman and West (Miller and Sutherland 2023, p. 105), James and Clarke and Anderson and Leaper detail contrasting findings from dozens of studies: many show men interrupt more than women, many show no difference between the sexes, and even some show that women interrupt more than men. Even though at the time of James & Clarke’s writing, “one of the findings most widely cited as well established is that men interrupt women more than women interrupt men,” they demonstrate that the finding was not shared across studies (James and Clarke, 1993, p. 231).

James and Clarke report that they found “no evidence” to support a gender difference in the number of interruptions initiated, reviewing results from dozens of studies that suggest a range of mediating factors. One is the *functional type* of interruption (competitive, cooperative, or neutral). They suggest a lack of gender difference in many research findings could be due to “the commonly held assumption that interruptions serve primarily to dominate and control conversations is overly simplistic.” Some evidence suggests women use more supportive interruptions such as simultaneous backchannels (one-word utterances such as “oh,” “yeah,” “uh-huh,” widely seen to indicate interest) (James and Clarke 1993 p. 235). Anderson and Leaper’s meta-analysis found a negligible effect size for the finding that men interrupt more than women, but also found a larger effect size for studies specifically looking at the “intrusive” type of interruption (1998). Other mediating factors mentioned by both reviews include semantic content (instances of agreement, clarification, or disagreement), the conversational context, the level of intimacy between the conversation participants, and more.

Definitions of interruption are inconsistent across studies, and there is no consensus in the linguistics and social science literature (Anderson and Leaper 1998; James and Clarke 1993). Three main types of definitions have been identified: (1) *general interruptions*, which are either undefined or have a broad range of criteria, including backchannels, mistiming errors (when a speaker mistakenly thinks another is ready to finish), and supportive overlaps; (2) studies that use an equally broad definition but exclude backchannels; and (3) studies that restrict the measurement to *intrusive interruptions*, “when a second speaker usurps another speaker’s right to continue speaking by taking the conversational floor in the absence of any evidence that the other speaker intended to relinquish the turn.” (Anderson and Leaper 1998, pp. 226, 233). The use of

this third definition would be aligned with the high-level of interest in the relationship between interruptions and power, but a lack of precedent for operationalization is a challenge. There have been no studies with reliable gauges of “whether or not an interruption constitutes a dominance attempt” (James and Clark 1993, p. 258).

The majority of early studies on gender difference in interruption face limitations in generalizability, since most of them rely on qualitative analysis of small samples, such as a manually annotated conversation between four people (Broadbridge 2003). Further, most studies involve “unacquainted or minimally acquainted college students interacting in dyads” in an “experimental laboratory” (James and Clarke, 1993, pp. 260-261). The lack of variety of relationships and research setting limits generalizability. Methodological concerns plague many studies, which failed to normalize the number of interruptions they counted with the amount of time each person spoke. Many had faulty or lacking statistical testing (James and Clark 1993). A few studies note that a speaker’s turn can be cut short without simultaneous speech occurring, and these instances are referred to as “silent interruptions,” which are ignored by most studies (James and Clarke 1993, p. 237). Most research has only focused on the gender of the interrupter, ignoring gender differences in likelihood of being interrupted or the interaction between the gender of the interrupter and the interruptee (James and Clark 1993, p. 267). So far, all studies examine only the man–woman gender binary. I have found no studies that investigate additional genders in conversation dynamics.

2.4. Opportunity for computational methods

The disagreement and lack of generalizability in the current literature presents an opportunity for computational methods. This is reinforced by the complex contextual factors that may influence interruption behavior, such as age, how well people know each other, status/power from non-gender sources, natural vs. laboratory setting, group size, and topic of conversation (James and Clarke 1993, Anderson and Leaper 1998). Computational tools like neural networks are well-suited to handle complex phenomena and large datasets, facilitating research designs that can account for mediating variables and produce generalizable results. The ability to analyze very large datasets could also enable the inclusion of additional genders, whose numbers in datasets often don’t have enough statistical power to allow researchers to draw conclusions about these groups.

2.5. Computational precedent

Only recently have studies on group differences in interruptions begun to use computational methods.

Boyd, Collins and Ringhand (2024) applied OLS regression to large datasets from US supreme court confirmation hearings. They found that “male and white participants are more likely to interrupt women and persons of color speakers, respectively, relative to male and white speakers” (p. 1). They do not mention how they generated their data, which included counts of the number of interruptions initiated for nominee-senator dyads. Without computational tools that allow them to automatically detect instances of interruptions either in text or in audiovisual data, the creation of this large dataset was likely labor-intensive.

Jacobi and Schweers (2017) and Miller and Sutherland (2023) applied simple text-based methods to study interruptions in transcripts of US supreme court oral arguments and congressional hearings, respectively. Both studies found that women members are more likely to be interrupted than men. The computational tools allowed Miller and Sutherland to also account for conversation topic, finding that women are more than twice as likely to be interrupted if the discussion is about women’s issues. Both studies exploited a feature of manually generated Government Printing Office (GPO) transcripts, counting em dashes after speech segments, which were added to the transcripts to denote interruptions. Unfortunately, interruption notation is not clearly delineated in automatically generated transcripts, limiting how widely this method can be applied.

Two papers external to the social sciences describe attempts at computational detection of interruptions in audio data. Caraty and Montacie (2015) used a support vector machine model, and in a May 2024 working paper, Lebourdais, Tahon, Laurent, and Meignier introduce their project to use a temporal convolutional neural network (TCN) to automatically detect interruptions in audio. At the time of this writing, no one has attempted to use audio classification machine learning sound event detection using a transformer, nor to investigate gender patterns in interruptions.

3. The case for audio transformers

Support vector machines and TCNs, rooted in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are older technologies. While CNNs were formerly the leading architecture for audio and visual machine learning tasks, neural networks with transformer architectures are considered state-of-the-art. In recent years transformer-based models trained on audio data for audio tasks such as WAV2VEC2, HuBERT, CLAP, and more, have been developed, offering the opportunity to leverage powerful self-attention mechanisms unique to transformers for better performance on audio tasks (Vaswani et al. 2017). Verma and Berger (2021) demonstrate transformer architectures that bring

significant improvements to audio task performance over CNNs.

For audio machine learning to be a viable method to study interruptions, this audio phenomenon must have distinct audio signatures. Audio data has three characteristics: amplitude (perceived as loudness) frequency (perceived as pitch), and time period (AlexSoft, 2022). These three characteristics can be measured numerically through decibels, hertz, and seconds. For machine learning, the numerical measurements of these patterns are encoded as vectors that are analyzed by the neural network (Hugging Face n.d.- a). In order for a phenomenon like interruptions to be perceivable through audio data by a machine learning model, it should have a specific signature in these dimensions.

The phenomenon of interest can be reasonably expected to be present in audio data. Audio classifiers can already detect binary gender classes with high reliability, often achieving F1 scores close to 1.0 (Uddin, Pathan, Hossain, and Biswas, 2021; Ertam 2019; Kacamarga et al. 2019; Alnuaim et al. 2022, Alefiury n.d.; Yang 2020). This demonstrates that the spectrum (range of frequencies) of men’s voices and women’s voices are distinct and can be identified by a machine learning model. Interruptions should also have an audio signature in order for this methodology to be viable. Multiple voices speaking at once are expected to increase the amplitude of the sound, making it louder. From the audio machine learning task of keyword spotting, we know that words have an audio signature, visible in patterns that a model can understand (Rai, Li, and Lyu 2023). Therefore, the out-of-sync overlap of multiple words spoken by more than one speaker could be expected to have a distinct pattern. Further, there are pitch behaviors indicating where a person is in a sentence: a down pitch indicates the end of a sentence, and an up-pitch indicates a question (among other things). An interrupter may have to jump in with a certain level of vigor in order to take attention away from the existing speaker, while the interruptee’s speech could lose “steam” as attention is drawn away. All of these could be manifested in loudness, pitch, or timing: the three dimensions that can be numerically captured and analyzed by a model.

While distinct interruption patterns can be reasonably hypothesized to exist in audio features, there may be many nuanced variations of them. For example, the silent interruption would not involve overlapping speech. The complexity of this task indicates that a neural network transformer architecture could be beneficial. The model will have to learn what patterns are important to pay attention to and what noise it can ignore. The self-attention mechanism of a transformer gives a model the ability to identify and focus on only

the task-relevant parts of an input by assigning weights (Vaswani et al. 2017). This allows a transformer to effectively “sift” through noise and make sense of complex phenomena, making it likely the best choice for complex audio tasks. The clear path forward in computational interruption detection is with transformers.

Political scientists have already begun to use machine learning audio techniques, including with transformers, to support a range of research interests. Rheault, Ludovic, and Borwein (2019) take advantage of the “ever-increasing” number of political events documented on video, finding that the use of image-processing deep neural networks on audio-visual data improves the detection of emotional affect compared to text-only data. Dietrich, Bryce, Ryan, and Maya (2019) used audio methods to detect emotional arousal in audio recordings of US supreme court oral arguments by measuring voice pitch, and then used that to accurately predict many of the justice’s eventual votes. Knox and Lucas (2021) demonstrate that even a latent variable such as skepticism in US supreme court justice’s speech can be detected using audio methods. These studies show the importance of audio techniques, which can capture information that would have been lost with transcription for text-based analysis.

This paper explores the use of audio machine learning methods with a transformer neural network model to identify interruptions and the gender dynamic. This method allows us to analyze extant audio data without transcription, leveraging nonverbal information present in speech that would be lost through transcription. It also allows the analysis of more sources, since researchers would no longer have to restrict their data to manual transcripts that explicitly code for interruption. Audio classifiers have the potential to be a more powerful method of interruption detection, with wider application potential than current text-based methods.

4. Defining an interruption

Since this project is one of the earliest attempts to computationally detect interruptions in audio, it requires a balance between a technically facilitative broad definition and the desire to support research on conversational power dynamics. I use a definition of the second type, broadly defining interruptions as “any deviation from a smooth switch between speakers,’ with no implication as to whether speaking rights are violated” but excluding simple backchannels (James and Clarke 1993, p. 238; Ferguson 1977).

In order to apply audio methods to this topic, operationalization must be firmly grounded in the audio characteristics of recorded speech (spectrum, intensity, and timing), so nuances that are more likely to depend

on semantics (using the meaning of words to differentiate speaker intent, for example) should be deemphasized to begin with. A broad definition that includes a variety of simultaneous speech gives the model an easier task, as it must learn only the more general patterns that characterize the phenomenon without having to differentiate several nuanced variations. This increases the chance of success even with smaller training datasets. Since I created my own custom training dataset, its size is constrained by the availability of my personal labor hours. When more data can be produced and working interruption-spotting models can be built-upon, investigations into which interruption nuances can be detected using audio would be possible.

A broad definition has subject-matter advantages. Simultaneous speech has multiple functions (competitive, supportive, neutral) that can reflect different social patterns (gender or cultural difference in supportive interruptions) that could be refined in future versions of the model. Tannen (1993) delineates the importance of recognizing multiple functions in order to avoid cultural biases. I include silent interruptions for their functional compatibility with the phenomenon of interest. While it may introduce complexity for the model, it is an important case, and I hypothesized that it still may have its own audio signature such as pitch or timing patterns. The exclusion of backchannels was acceptable from a technical perspective because keyword spotting is a common audio classification task, so an audio model should be able to recognize the audio signature of short specific few-syllable simultaneous utterances (Hugging Face, n.d.-b).

5. Method

5.1. Audio classification method

The task of identifying interruptions in audio data is an audio classification task. I call the task *interruption spotting* given the similarities to the audio machine learning task of *keyword spotting*, a classic audio sequence classification task. Both fall under the category of sound event detection. In these tasks, a base audio model is fine-tuned in a supervised manner to recognize patterns in numerical representations of the audio waveform in the form of numerical vectors. The model is asked to assign a label to a series of fixed length sequences of numbers (snippets of the waveform) based on a probability distribution associated with the likelihood of the segment belonging to each class.

5.1.1. Audio data collection

The training data for this project was derived from manual annotation of interruptions observed in 10

podcast episodes, each from a different series with different casting to maximize the variety of speakers in the training data. Most podcasts in the training data are comedy podcasts, a genre chosen for active conversations with a high number of interruptions. Episodes with mixed-gender groups were prioritized, but some podcasts with homogenous gender makeup were added to the sample in order to achieve a better class balance, which is important to avoid bias in the classifiers.

Inference was conducted on 43 podcast episodes from the same podcast series that were used in the training data set. Episodes with at least 2 men and 2 women were used to approximate controlled conditions.

Podcasts are a good source of data because they are an accessible source of conversational “found” data with the benefits of being “big” and “nonreactive” (Salganik 2017). The natural observed conversations in podcasts are more likely to offer realistic examples of interruptions and interruption dynamics than those that would be observed in a laboratory. They present a clear opportunity for a large dataset: as of December 2024, there are more than 4.3 million podcasts registered with podcastindex.org, providing countless hours of pre-recorded conversation, dwarfing the 6-person laboratory observation model of the past. Big data tools and methods enable the social data scientist to repurpose this entertainment format for research.

5.1.2. Base audio model

The base model used in this task is DistilHuBERT. This is a distilled version of Hidden-unit BERT (HuBERT), a neural network model that consists of a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a transformer encoder (Chang, Yang, and Lee 2022). HuBERT is a self-supervised model for speech representation learning with 95M to 1B parameters and competitive performance on several speech tasks (Hsu et al. 2021). HuBERT is a good choice also because “speech recognition models that have been pre-trained in unsupervised fashion on audio data alone, e.g. Wav2Vec2, HuBERT, XLSR-Wav2Vec2, have shown to require only very little annotated data to yield good performance on speech classification datasets” (Hugging Face 2021). While the number of parameters brings very high training costs, the distilled version reduces the size by 75%, making it 73% faster while retaining most of its performance (Chang, Yang and Lee 2022).

DistilHuBERT is well-suited to the task of fine-tuning for interruption spotting, including the labeling of the gender dynamic in the interruption because it is pre-trained on speech data, blends the traditional audio architecture of CNNs with the power of transformers,

performs well on a number of speech tasks, and can be expected to perform well in audio classification tasks after fine-tuning on limited training data.

5.1.3. Audio classifiers

I trained two separate fine-tuned DistilHuBERT interruption spotting models: a binary classifier designed to identify interruptions without gender information, and a multi-class classifier designed to identify an interruption along with the gender of the speakers involved.

Interruption spotting audio classifier

The first classifier was trained in a binary classification task. It was designed to answer the question: can a fine-tuned DistilHuBERT model be trained to identify an interruption vs. a non-interruption? This was an important intermediate step towards determining if interruption gender classification is possible. If an audio model cannot identify interruptions, then it cannot identify interruptions based on the gender dynamic. Two classes were relevant for this model as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Classes for the interruption spotting classifier

0	non-interruption
1	interruption

Interruptions by gender audio classifier

Once performance of the binary classifier showed that a model can successfully learn to identify an interruption, the classifier was expanded to include gender and answer the following question: can a fine-tuned DistilHuBERT model be trained to identify an interruption by the genders of the speakers involved? This classifier was trained to classify a segment of speech into one of 5 classes, shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Classes for the interruptions by gender classifier

0	non-interruption	
1	M-W	man interrupting a woman
2	M-M	man interrupting a man
3	W-W	woman interrupting a woman
4	M-W	woman interrupting a woman

A binary gender classification with only two genders is used because the training data included only men and women. Future models should be developed to incorporate more genders.

5.1.4. Audio operationalization

Short audio segments each containing one example of an interruption or non-interruption comprised the

data. The examples were on average 2.19 seconds long, up to 5.92 seconds. Audio before the interruption and after the interruption is included in the segment, reasoning that in order for the model to identify the gender dynamic, it must have access to the voice of the speaker that was speaking first. The voice of the second speaker could be additional information to help with this classification. Examples with simultaneous speech involving three or more speakers were excluded, as well as simultaneous starts where a clear temporal relationship (who spoke first) between the speakers was not present. There were few instances of these cases in the audio from which the training data was extracted. All interruption attempts were included, whether or not the interrupter successfully took the floor.

5.1.5. Audio training data

To fine-tune DistilHuBERT, I assembled a custom training dataset with 3,076 examples that includes an equal number of interruptions (further classified by gender) and non-interruptions. The examples were obtained by manually labeling instances of interruptions and non-interruption using the software Label Studio. To ensure the model doesn't learn a gender bias in what it considers an interruption, the non-interruption examples were constructed to contain equal numbers of female and male voices. Table 3 shows the label distribution in the training data.

Table 3. Training data label distribution

Label	Count
Interruption	1,538
man interrupting woman [M-W]	336
woman interrupting woman [W-W]	404
woman interrupting man [W-M]	405
man interrupting man [M-M]	393
Non-interruptions	1,538
Total	3,076

5.1.6. Audio model training

For the binary interruption-spotting classifier, training was performed using leave-one-out cross-validation. In each of 10 folds, all examples from one podcast episode were omitted from the training data. These examples were used as the validation data for the fold. This allowed me to determine that the classifier can extrapolate what it learned about interruption patterns to new voices that it had never heard, illustrating how well the model can learn the unique audio characteristics of an interruption regardless of the voice. Each fold was trained with 10 epochs.

The multiclass gender classifier was trained using an 80-20 split for 10 epochs. Leave-one-out cross

validation was not useful in this case, because several podcasts lacked one or more classes. The 80-20 split produced more meaningful metrics as all classes were included in the test data.

5.1.7. Audio inference

To demonstrate how a future fine-tuned model could be applied to social science research, I performed an inference exercise using the multiclass gender classifier. The model was used to identify instances of interruptions and their gender dynamic on 43 unseen audio files. This inference dataset included episodes from a subset of the same podcasts that were used in the training data. All episodes that had at least two men and two women were included. I restricted the inference sample to groups with this gender makeup to approximate controlled conditions, since group size was shown to possibly influence interruption behavior (James and Clarke 1993).

Interruption counts are directly related to speaking time (James and Clarke 1993). For example, if men speak more than women during a conversation, there is more opportunity for men to be interrupted. To control for this, I normalize the inferred interruption counts by the number of minutes each gender spoke. An existing gender voice classifier, Alefiury's (n.d.) fine-tuned version of facebook/wav2vec2-xls-r-300m for gender recognition (F1 0.9993), was used to obtain the total number of minutes in these podcasts spoken by women and the number of minutes spoken by men. The interruption counts were then divided by the number of speaking minutes of the interruptee to calculate the number of interruptions per minute of speaking time.

The goal of this inference exercise was to demonstrate the potential of the audio classifier methodology for interruption spotting. Consequently, proper social science sampling techniques were not followed in the assembly of the inference sample. Therefore, the numerical results should not be considered valid findings and cannot be extrapolated. Further, the internal validity of the inference results is compromised by the imperfect performance of the classifier. These results should not be construed with rigorous research findings on interruption rates by gender.

5.2. Text classification method

The state-of-the-art computational interruption detection by gender in the social sciences is the text-based method used by Jacobi and Schweers (2017) and Miller and Sutherland (2023). The team took advantage of a specific feature of transcripts manually produced by GPO transcriptionists: interruptions that were flagged by en or em dashes at the end of a chunk of speech. To better understand what kind of advantage, if any, audio

classification could provide over text-based methods (which are generally better developed than audio methods in the machine learning world), I tested the performance of this text method and three similar methods on automatically generated transcripts of three podcasts.

5.2.1. Text data

I generated diarized transcripts of three podcast episodes using WhisperX Large V3. The three episodes were chosen for their even distribution of gender in the cast. Transcripts consisted of a series of distinct short speech segments that the model identified along with the segment's associated start and end times and speaker labels. The transcriber model appeared to generate fairly accurate speaker diarization and very accurate word transcription, but it made many diarization mistakes at speaker transitions, especially when speech overlaps were involved. I manually reviewed the entire transcripts and corrected speaker assignments.

5.2.2. Text classifiers

I employed four rule-based text classification methods to find interruptions in the transcripts. The first method is the same rule-based method used by Jacobi and Schweers (2017) and Miller and Sutherland (2022), which involved finding speaker segments that ended with a punctuation flagging an interruption. WhisperX Large V3 inserted both ellipses and dashes for various purposes in the transcript, so I included both. If a speaker segment ended with one of these punctuations and was followed by a segment by a different speaker, then the transition was classified as an interruption.

The second method involved identifying speech segments that ended in incomplete sentences and was followed by a segment with a new speaker. Two definitions of incomplete sentences were used: (1) if the sentence lacked ending punctuation, and (2) if the sentence lacked a subject and a finite verb. The transcripts generated by the speech-to-text model included punctuation and were observed to have a high word accuracy during manual proofing. Therefore, incomplete sentences should be accurately represented in the transcript.

The third and fourth methods were designed to exploit the time-stamp data that the transcription included with each speech segment. For the third method, the classifier identified segments with different speakers that overlapped in time. The test of this method led to the discovery that the transcriber handled overlapping speech by prioritizing one speaker and artificially forcing almost all segments into temporal adjacency (no overlap). I therefore developed the fourth

classifier which would look for very fast speaker switches as a criterion for identifying an interruption. All four methods are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Rule-based text classifiers for interruption spotting

ID	Method	Operationalization
1	ellipses and dashes ^a	A speaker segment that fulfills the criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ends with (...) (-) (—) (—) • is followed by a segment by a different speaker.
2	incomplete sentences	A speaker segment that fulfills the criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ends with an incomplete sentence • is followed by a segment by a different speaker. <p>Two operationalizations of an incomplete sentence were tested:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The segment ends without sentence-ending punctuation such as . ! ? 2) The final sentence in the segment doesn't have a subject and finite verb.
3	overlapping segments	A speaker segment that fulfills the criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ends later than the following segment, and • is followed by a segment by a different speaker.
4	fast speaker switch	A speaker segment that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ends less than 0.1 seconds before the following segment • is followed by a segment by a different speaker.

^aUsed by Jacobi and Schweers (2017) and Miller and Sutherland (2023)

Gender was assigned to all detected interruptions by extracting the speaker ID for the relevant speech segments. The speaker IDs were manually assigned their gender based on the cast of the podcast. Since speaker assignments for each segment were manually corrected, the gender dimension of the interruption is expected to be highly accurate. To obtain classification metrics, the timestamps of detected interruptions were matched to the timestamps of ground-truth labeled interruptions from the audio training set with a flexible overlap condition, and labels were compared.

6. Results

Classification metrics for fine-tuning of the binary audio classifier (determining whether a transformer model can be trained to detect interruptions) are promising. Performance of the multiclass classifier (showing whether or not a model can be trained to detect interruption along with their gender dynamic) are not as good, likely due to the limited training data, but still encouraging. All four rule-based classifiers that were designed to detect interruptions and their gender in diarized transcripts showed very poor performance, in large part due to the limitations of the WhisperX Large V3 transcripts, as well as inherent limitations of text to retain relevant data about conversation dynamics.

6.1. Interruption spotting audio classifier results

The first audio task, which determined whether or not a fine-tuned DistilHuBERT model could be trained to differentiate interruptions and non-interruptions (ignoring gender), showed consistent promising results across folds in leave-one-out cross validation. Average performance metrics ranged between 0.83 and 0.87, indicating that with enhancements such as a larger, more diverse dataset, such a model could approach very reliable performance.

Table 5 displays the performance metrics from the final epoch (epoch 10) of each fold and the average performance across folds. Average metrics are quite consistent between accuracy, precision, recall, and F1, indicating that the model is performing consistently across the tasks, like a result of perfect class balance in the training data.

Table 5. Interruption spotting audio classifier performance for each fold and averaged across folds

Fold	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
1	0.77	0.72	0.88	0.79
2	0.89	0.91	0.87	0.89
3	0.84	0.85	0.84	0.84
4	0.85	0.85	0.86	0.86
5	0.90	0.87	0.95	0.91
6	0.81	0.77	0.88	0.82
7	0.87	0.86	0.87	0.87
8	0.82	0.78	0.89	0.83
9	0.85	0.86	0.84	0.85
10	0.82	0.85	0.77	0.81
Average	0.84	0.83	0.87	0.85

In each fold, the training data from one entire podcast is excluded from the training data. Validation for that fold is conducted exclusively on the examples from the excluded podcast. Consistent results across folds (with some exceptions, such as metrics that dip below 0.8 in folds 1, 6, and 10) indicate that the model can learn important characteristics of an interruption and extrapolate that successfully to new voices it has never heard before. The training data has enough diversity to help the model learn and successfully extrapolate the characteristics of an interruption.

6.2. Interruptions by gender audio classifier results

The performance of the multi-class classifier that was trained to identify the gender dynamic along with an interruption was 0.10–0.20 lower than with the binary classifier. This is to be expected for a more technically challenging task, especially with fewer examples of each class to learn from. Table 6 shows the

performance results of all ten training epochs. Metrics steadily evolve showing the model optimized well.

Table 6. Interruptions by gender audio classifier training results across 10 training epochs

Epoch	Training Loss	Validation Loss	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
1	1.0174	0.9472	0.63	0.65	0.48	0.46
2	0.8360	0.7681	0.69	0.71	0.58	0.54
3	0.6057	0.6506	0.74	0.75	0.66	0.59
4	0.6317	0.6217	0.74	0.77	0.66	0.60
5	0.4478	0.6077	0.74	0.70	0.68	0.62
6	0.4757	0.6491	0.75	0.71	0.65	0.62
7	0.3686	0.6066	0.76	0.76	0.67	0.64
8	0.3194	0.5860	0.76	0.73	0.68	0.64
9	0.3234	0.5652	0.76	0.71	0.68	0.64
10	0.3228	0.5703	0.77	0.72	0.69	0.66

Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging.

Overall accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 are less balanced than in the binary task, with recall and F1 consistently lower than accuracy and precision. Class-specific metrics, shown in Table 7, provide insight into classification patterns. The model classified non-interruptions most effectively, likely due to it being the class with the highest singular representation (1,538 examples). Precision for M-W and M-M are at or approaching 90% indicating that out of all of the cases of these classes that the model predicted, a very large number were correct. Importantly however, the extremely low recall for M-W (0.08) means that the model failed to catch most instances of this class. With very high precision and very low recall, the model appears to predict this class only when it is very confident that a man is interrupting a woman before it assigns the label. Consequently, it is underpredicting these cases.

Table 7. Interruptions by gender audio classifier performance metrics by class

Class	Precision	Recall	F1
Non-interruption	0.84	0.92	0.88
M-W	0.86	0.08	0.15
M-M	0.90	0.72	0.80
W-M	0.49	0.80	0.61
W-W	0.73	0.83	0.78

Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging. Accuracy of each class is equivalent to combined accuracy values.

In contrast, higher recall rates for W-M and W-W relative to lower precision scores for these categories, especially W-M, indicate that the model is overpredicting these categories. Lower precision indicates a higher number of false positives, while higher recall points means that a higher share of the true positives were identified. We can conclude that the

model is more comfortable predicting cases where women are the interrupters, in contrast to its reticence in predicting cases where men are the interrupters. It appears to be “overconfident” in its determination that a woman is an interrupter. Since the number of training examples of each interruption type is so low, this possibly could be due to the fact that the classes where women are interrupters had more examples in the training data than the classes where men are interrupters.

It must be further noted that the lowest scores correspond to the two mix-gender interruption classes, indicating that distinguishing between these classes is the hardest subtask. Recall for M-W is 0.08, meaning the model failed to identify the vast majority of men interrupting women. A precision score of 0.49 for W-M indicates that the model is incorrectly predicting this class notably more than the other classes.

The two classes representing gender-heterogenous interruptions are the only two that require the model to determine speaker order. It is clearly a much more complex task to determine which is the interrupter and which is the interruptee. When the model identifies an interruption that involves two voices of the same gender, once it knows the gender of these speakers, the classification has been made. There is only one choice for two men (M-M) and only one choice for two women (W-W). No determination about who was speaking first is necessary. However, once it detects an interruption with mixed-gender voices, it now has to choose between M-W and W-M. It must determine which voice it hears first and which it hears second in the segment. Even though the class balance in the training dataset was not extreme (see Table 3), M-W was the least represented class in the training dataset, with 336 examples. In contrast, W-M was the most represented interruption type with 405 examples. Since this number of examples of each class is so low for machine learning, the difference of 69 examples may have been enough to bias the model against M-W given the particular difficulty of the task.

When this model is used for inference on unseen data, we can expect it to greatly underpredict instances of men interrupting, missing the majority of cases of men interrupting women. It will also likely overpredict instances of women interrupting, especially women interrupting men.

6.3. Text classifier results

Performance of the four rule-based text classifiers was generally poor, due in large part to the limitations of the diarized transcript produced by WhisperX Large V3, as well as inherent limitations of text data to convey spoken conversation dynamics.

Text method 1, ellipses and dashes

This rule identified an interruption as a speaker segment that ended with an ellipses, hyphen, en dash, or em dash and was followed by a segment by a new speaker. WhisperX did not assign signifiers such as ellipses and dashes reliably to interruptions. Across the three transcripts, 364 ellipses, 118 hyphens, 118 en dashes, and 0 em dashes occurred in total. However, they did not reliably signal an interruption, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Performance of the ellipses and dashes text classifier

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Interruption spotting	0.47	0.24	0.11	0.15
Interruptions by gender ^a	0.45	0.15	0.07	0.09

^a Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging.

The high accuracy scores were likely driven by the true negative count of non-interruptions that it did not classify. Low precision, recall, and F1 scores indicate that there were many interruptions that the model either failed to detect or assigned the incorrect gender classification. Low precision indicates many false positives: instances where a segment transition met the criteria, but the ellipses or dashes were not related to an interruption. There could be instances where a speaker trailed off without finishing their statement and the model inserted ellipses. Recall values are especially low at 0.11 for the binary task and 0.07 for the multiclass task, indicating that out of the ground-truth positives, the model caught very few of them. This method is a poor way to identify interruptions when applied to automatically generated transcripts.

Text method 2a, incomplete sentences by punctuation

This classifier identified an interruption by finding a speech segment that does not end with proper end-of-sentence punctuation and is followed by a speech segment with a new speaker. This method performed very poorly, with accuracy below 0.4 for both the binary and multiclass condition, and precision, recall, and F1 below 0.2. Low precision indicates many false positives, and low recall signals that most true interruptions were not caught by the model.

Table 9. Performance of the incomplete sentences by punctuation text classifier

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Interruption spotting	0.39	0.17	0.19	0.18
Interruptions by gender ^a	0.36	0.10	0.11	0.10

^a Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging.

Text method 2b, incomplete sentences by grammar

Identifying incomplete sentences based on grammar performed even worse by most measures. The predictions were very inaccurate, with scores below 0.2. The very high recall at 0.88 for the binary conditions says that this model was able to find most of the true interruptions, but combined with an extremely low precision, we know that most predictions it made were incorrect. The model predicted 2,752 interruptions across three transcripts, the highest so far. It appears to have simply predicted a very high number of interruptions without much accuracy at all. Once the gender dimension is mapped to these interruptions, the recall value was reduced by more than half.

Table 10. Performance of the incomplete sentences by grammar text classifier

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Interruption spotting	0.16	0.13	0.88	0.22
Interruptions by gender ^a	0.10	0.06	0.42	0.11

^a Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging.

This is likely due to this method being a poor operationalization of an interruption. For example, many statements made in these spoken conversations did not consist of complete sentences. Simple statements such as “right, right,” “feels great,” “on time, thank you,” “one hundred percent,” and many more appear very common in spoken conversation. This is a severe limitation of using this method to identify interruptions. Therefore, incomplete sentences alone appear to be a poor way to operationalize interruptions.

Text method 3, speech segment time overlap

The third classifier was designed to identify an interruption by finding two speech segments with overlapping timestamps and different speakers. Since most of the interruptions annotated for the training dataset involved overlapping speech, this was a promising method. However, the record low classification metrics indicate a severe barrier to using this method. With a precision of 0.18 and recall of 0.00, we can conclude the 0.49 accuracy is essentially exclusively due to the ground-truth non-interruptions that the model did not detect.

Table 11. Performance of the speech segment time overlap text classifier

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Interruption spotting	0.49	0.18	0.00	0.01
Interruptions by gender ^a	0.49	0.02	0.00	0.00

^a Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging.

Across all three transcripts, the model only found 9 cases it classified as an interruption. Inspection of the transcripts revealed that there were almost no overlapping timestamps between speech segments. WhisperX Large V3 model appears to have handled overlapping speech by prioritizing one speaker, erasing some simultaneous speech, and artificially forcing all segments that are captured to be temporally adjacent. The quality of transcription diarization technology at speaker transitions in particular is the single most limiting factor in the application of what could have been an effective method.

Text method 4, fast speaker switches

The fourth classifier was a variation on the speech-segment overlap classifier, investigating whether very fast times between segments of different speakers could instead be used. If the model struggled to handle overlapping segments, it might force them into temporal adjacency but with very close time stamps. A threshold of 0.1 second between segments with different speakers was used.

This method also performed very poorly. Accuracy was lower than in the speech overlap segment, indicating a high number of false predictions. Recall was the lowest for this method, 0.16 and 0.10 for the binary and multiclass tasks respectively, which indicates that many detected interruptions were false positives.

Table 12. Performance of the fast speaker switch text classifier

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Interruption spotting	0.29	0.16	0.44	0.23
Interruptions by gender ^a	0.24	0.10	0.24	0.13

^a Precision, recall, and F1 were calculated using macro-averaging.

The dismal classification metrics of all four of these methods demonstrate the reliance of text-based methods on transcript quality, and for text data to capture nonverbal elements of spoken conversation. The speech-to-text model, while accurate with words and generally with speaker assignment, made many mistakes at speaker transitions, regions that are crucial in identifying interruptions. Even with speaker assignments manually corrected, none of these methods can be used.

Until the technology for automatic speech transcription evolves to handle speaker transitions and overlapping speech better (both of which are audio machine learning tasks in and of themselves), rule-based classifiers like the one used by Jacobi and Schweers (2017) and Miller and Sutherland (2022) cannot be widely applied to recorded speech that must first be automatically transcribed. Considering the high cost of labor-intensive manual transcription, the

practicality of audio-based methods is clear. The direct analysis of audio allows the data to maintain many of the unique nonverbal data about spoken conversation that are lost through transcription.

7. Audio inference

To illustrate the potential social science research application of the audio methodology developed in this project, the gender classifier model was used to infer interruptions and gender dynamic on 43 unseen podcast episodes. When a reliable gender interruption model is trained on a larger dataset with a better class balance, it can be applied to unseen data and trusted to capture the correct number interruptions per class. This can be applied to well-designed samples to draw conclusions about gender behavior as it relates to discussion topic, setting, group-size, and much more. Counts could, for example, be combined with data on control variables and analyzed with regression analysis to provide statistically rigorous insight into many complex interruption dynamics. However, it is beyond the scope of this methodological proof-of-concept project to employ proper social science sampling and research design techniques, so these inference results should not be construed with valid research findings about gendered interruption behavior.

Based on the model's imperfect performance metrics, we should expect inaccuracy in the inference results. This is especially true in the M-W and W-M classes, given the diverging precision and recall rates these two classes have. Since inference is performed on unlabeled, unseen data, we cannot evaluate the classification but can interpret trends in the predictions.

Table 13 shows the total number and proportion of interruptions found in these 43 podcast episodes, by class. Already we can see that the class with the lowest recall value (M-W) is, as expected, the least detected class by far. Interruptions where men interrupt women comprise only 5.8% of the interruptions. Due to low recall for this class, the model probably missed most instances of this interruption type.

Table 13. Total inferred interruption counts from 43 podcast episodes, by class

	W (Interruptee)	M (Interruptee)	All
W (Interrupter)	2,941 (13.7%)	7,087 (32.9%)	10,028 (46.6%)
M (Interrupter)	1,239 (5.8%)	10,246 (47.6%)	11,485 (53.4%)
All	4,180 (19.5%)	17,333 (80.5%)	2,1513 (100.0%)

Knowing the amount of time members of each gender spent speaking helps us to more accurately understand how their interruption behavior compares. As discussed previously, this metric is an important mediating variable for the raw number of interruptions, because a speaker's likelihood of being interrupted is

directly connected to how much time they spend speaking (James and Clarke 1993). A gender classifier was applied to the sample to infer the number of minutes spoken by men and the number of minutes spoken by women. Results are shown in Table 14. Across podcasts, despite an almost even casting split between men and women, men spoke more than 60% of the time and women spoke less than 40% of the time. There were more opportunities for men to be interrupted and fewer opportunities for women to be interrupted.

Table 14. Gender speaking time inference results for 43 podcast episodes

Gender	Speaking time, minutes	Percentage of time spoken
Women	1,198.80	38.02%
Men	1,953.90	61.98%

Raw interruption counts were divided by the number of speaking minutes of the interruptee to calculate the interruption rate: the number of interruptions per minute of speaking time (Table 15). If the model were reliable, this would allow us to infer that, for example, on average, women interrupted men 3.6 times per minute that men were speaking (likely over-predicted, given class metrics). Men interrupted women on average 1 time per minute that women were speaking (certainly under-identified given class metrics). Men interrupt men 5.2 times per minute that a man is speaking. And on average, women interrupt women 2.5 times per minute that a woman is speaking. Women were interrupted on average 3.5 times per minute that they were speaking, and men were interrupted 8.8 times per minute that they were speaking.

Table 15. Interruptions per minute, normalized by interruptee speaking time

	W (Interruptee)	M (Interruptee)
W (Interrupter)	2.5	3.6
M (Interrupter)	1	5.2
All	3.5	8.8

These numbers are for demonstration of the methodology only. Bias in the classifier and less-than-ideal performance metrics compromise internal validity for these findings. A lack of proper sampling techniques in the creation of the inference sample prevents us from extrapolating. No meaning should be drawn from these numbers. Once the methodology is refined and a reliable classifier is established, proper sampling and statistical techniques can be used to achieve valid results.

8. Discussion

The results show reason for optimism for the use of audio machine learning classifiers as a social science research tool to research gender differences in interruption behavior. Even with a dataset of only 1,538 interruptions and 1,538 non-interruption examples, a binary interruption spotting classifier successfully identified interruptions, even among voices it had not heard before, achieving metrics above 0.80. With a larger dataset consisting of even more diverse voices used to train larger transformer models like HuBERT, it is very likely that these metrics can be improved. Data augmentation techniques provide a convenient next step to investigate the power of more training data.

While the gender classifier performed a bit worse, it is still promising to have achieved classification results from 0.66 to 0.77 with a very small number of examples (as low as 339) in each class. This was significantly better than all four text-based methods, showing promise for the ability of transformer models to learn representations that capture interruptions by gender when a more appropriate amount of balanced training data is available.

8.1. The potential of audio methods

A preponderance of recorded audio data is available to social data scientists with the tools to leverage it. The availability of an audio-based method like the one explored in this paper greatly expands researcher access to large amounts of “found” speech data. Until transcription technology improves, the potential for widespread analysis of interruptions using text is limited, and only expensive, manually generated transcripts with deliberate interruption flags can be used. At the current state of audio classification and speech-to-text technology, it is easier and more effective to apply an audio classifier than to transcribe the conversation and use text methods.

As discussed, the class-specific metrics point to the difficulty of differentiating gender-heterogenous interruptions. There are three clear ways to potentially improve model performance in this subtask. First, by providing more training data. A larger (and therefore more appropriate) number of examples for each class, with perfect class balance, would give the model more information from which to learn the important patterns and allow the model to learn all four patterns equally well. Second, a larger model with more parameters could keep track of nuances in audio patterns that are essential for such a complex task. When more training data is available, the full HuBERT model offers these advantages, and other large models like Wav2Vec2 could be tested. Third, the operationalization could be adjusted to include more context before the interruption. The model appears to require more

context to determine the speaking order of gender-heterogenous interruptions. This could be accomplished by increasing the length of each example to include more pre-interruption context, giving the model a larger segment to determine the gender spectrum of the speech before the interruption occurred. Whether or not the interruption was successful, and therefore which speaker took the floor and spoke alone at the end of an interruption is irrelevant. Sufficient data to determine the gender of the first speaker could be enough to make this determination and correctly classify the gender dynamic of gender-heterogenous interruptions.

8.2. Further developments for text methods

Speech-to-text technology is evolving. OpenAI’s WhisperX, the version of the famous Whisper model enhanced with speaker diarization, was released in 2023, only very recently (Bain, Huh, Han, and Zisserman 2023). Diarization technology will likely be developed to better handle speaker switches and overlaps. Once temporal adjacency of transcribed speech segments is no longer forced and accurate timestamps reflecting simultaneous speech are generated, the use of simple rule-based methods like overlap detection in machine-generated transcripts could become much more effective. On this point there is symbiosis: projects like this, which train models to learn what interruption representations look like, contribute to the body of knowledge that could give speech-to-text technology the ability to handle speech overlaps more effectively.

This analysis did not include a comparison to text-based machine learning methods, which could yield different results. In such an exercise, a transformer model like BERT trained on text representations could be fed a set of pre-annotated interruption examples and counterexamples. From these, it would learn a more complex set of text characteristics that make up an interruption and learn to make a prediction on unseen speaker transitions. However, such a method is likely to be constrained by the same transcription-based limitations faced by the rule-based classifiers. Additionally, the unique interruption signature it learns might largely consist of the features already investigated with the rule-based classifiers, such as punctuation, grammar, or time-based patterns. Lastly, there is likely little or no inherent data about the speaker’s gender in the information conveyed through text. So text-based machine learning interruption detection would be combined with a programmatic gender label assignment like the one I used here. In audio machine learning, the task is simplified in that the machine can detect interruption and gender characteristics simultaneously.

8.3. Limitations

The operationalization of an interruption for this study assumes a two-party speech interaction with a clear sequential relationship. There is a clear first speaker who has the floor and a speaker that then interjects out of turn. Miller and Sutherland identify a type of interruption they call a “brouhaha,” which would involve three or more people and lacks a sequential relationship between them, characterized by “rapid-fire clusters in which [participants] fight for control of the conversation, which... is an especially aggressive form of interruption” (Miller and Sutherland 2022, p. 106). Due to my operational requirement for a sequential relationship between two speakers, I did not have a way to account for this type of interaction. It was excluded from the training dataset. While this may be a common occurrence in a political setting like the research subject of Miller and Sutherland, it was rare in my training dataset and therefore could represent a small number of misclassifications in inference on unseen data. Future audio classification research could investigate a separate audio category for this type of interaction. If it has distinct audio characteristics, a machine learning model could learn to differentiate this from the dyad-based interruptions.

My training data had a few instances of simultaneous starts. These were instances where a clear speaker transition point became available in the conversation and two or more people attempted to take the floor simultaneously. Similar to the brouhaha, this event also lacks a clear sequential relationship between speakers. Further research could investigate where these could be identified based on, for example, silence before the simultaneous speech, and determine a gender dynamic based on who “won” and got to speak alone after the event. This could be a relevant contribution to the power dynamic of a conversation. The simultaneous start was a rare event in the sample from which I drew my training data and was excluded from the examples prepared for training.

My operationalization excluded if one person was interrupted by two people at the same time. This was also a rare event and was excluded from the training data. Once basic interruption models like the ones explored in this project are refined, the possibility of training them to identify the genders of three speakers involved in one overlap event could be explored. Given the state of speaker diarization technology, prioritizing one voice at a time, this likely is a complex task.

8.4. Future research

Past interruption literature such as those reviewed by James and Clarke (1993) and Andersen and Leaper (1998) indicate moderating factors that can influence

gender differences in interruption behavior. Once basic classification models like the ones explored in this paper are refined and produce robust results, further audio classification models that investigate some of these factors could be explored. Only factors that can be reflected in the audio characteristics of intensity, spectrum, and time could be researched using audio techniques. So, information that is portrayed purely semantically such as the functional type (competitive, supportive, or neutral) might not be as easily captured by an audio model. Nonetheless, there is reason to be optimistic: past audio research has shown that even latent variables such as skepticism can indeed be detected and learned by audio machine learning models (Knox and Lucas 2021).

Insofar as interruption intent information may be semantic, hybrid methods that blend text and audio may yield effective for detection and classification of interruptions into functional type (competitive, supportive, or neutral). The interruption itself and the gender dynamic could be detected with audio, and those detections can be further classified by functional intent with a text-based classifier that can capture and analyze the semantic representations of words.

Literature suggests that gender is not the only relevant social dimension in interruption behavior (Boyd, Collins, and Ringhand 2024; James & Clarke 1993). Similar audio classification tools could be developed that learn interruptions based on other social dynamics. Audio classifiers exist that can classify voice by age and speaker accent, for example (audEERING GmbH n.d.; Do, Imai, Doddipatla, and Hain 2024). Any social division related to distinct speech characteristics could be investigated with this method.

Research into gender speaking patterns that include additional genders could be complex but informative and valuable. Since members of these groups often have very small numeric representation in data, computational methods that enable analysis of very large datasets can make it possible to more easily include these groups in the future.

9. Conclusion

This project contributes to interruption research methodology by showing how transformer models trained on speech audio data can learn representations of interruptions and their gender dynamic. The preliminary results shown in this paper suggest that with a larger number of more diverse examples of each interruption type with fully balanced classes, a transformer model could be trained to identify and classify interruptions by gender. This is simpler and more effective at present than using transcription and text methods.

The development and refinement of this tool would lay the groundwork for the investigation of a wide range of social research questions related to the factors that influence gender differences in interruption behavior, such as speaker relationship, conversation topic, group size, task context, and more. It could expand the power of social scientists to account for these mediating factors while producing generalizable results. There is also research potential in the future combined use of audio and text methods. Such a blended approach would leverage both sound and semantic data for a

potentially even more powerful tool to understand intent (competitive, supportive, and neutral interruptions), perhaps offering a path to create the first reliable gauge of whether an interruption qualifies as a dominance attempt (James and Clarke 1993). This technique could likely be applied to interruptions and other social divisions related to factors like age and accent. Researchers interested in the social dynamics of conversation interruptions have reason to explore to computational audio methods for ways to generate knowledge on an unprecedented scale.

10. LLM Disclosure

ChatGPT was used in this project in the following ways: to explore and inform analytical methods, guide in drafting, debugging, and proofing code, format citations, initially identify legal considerations, and identify academic papers. It was not used to generate writing.

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